

birds were weighed every week in electronic weighing balance.

Results and Discussion

The mean egg and hatch weight were 583.46 ± 20.87 g and 414.14 ± 5.47 g respectively. The hatch weights was 70.98 percent of egg weight. This is in agreement with Deeming and Ar (*loc. cit.*). The mean body weight of emu chicks during first week was 325.30 ± 9.07 g which was 21.45% less than the hatch weight. This observation is in agreement with Guittin (1987), Degen *et al.* (1991) and Deeming *et al.* (1993) who have reported that ratite chick loose up to 20% of their mass within 5 to 7 days of hatching. The poor or negative weight gain in young emu chick during the first few days of life recorded could be due to loss of body fluids and the utilization of yolk material up to 1 week post hatch.

The mean body weight of emu chicks

from 2nd to 10th week of age recorded were 617.30 ± 11.05 g; 800.00 ± 11.44 g; 1.46 ± 0.02 kg; 1.93 ± 0.02 kg; 2.86 ± 0.03 kg; 3.64 ± 0.04 kg; 4.81 ± 0.02 kg; 5.82 ± 0.03 kg and 6.85 ± 0.03 kg respectively. From 2nd week of age onwards there was a steady increase in body weight up to 10 week of age. In this study livability recorded up to 10 week of age was 100 percent.

References

- Degen, A.A., Kam, ., Rosenstrauch, A. and Plavnik, I. (1991) *Animal Prod.*, **52**: 225
- Deeming, D.C., Ayres, L. and Ayres, F.J. (1993) *Veterinary Record*. **132**:602
- Deeming, D.C. and Ar, A. (1999) CABI Publishing, Wallingford, Oxon, UK
- Guittin, P. (1987) *Canadian Journal of Zoology*, **65**:3056
- Jarvis, M.J.F. (1998) Proceedings of the 2nd International Ratite Congress, Oudts hoorn, South Africa. pp: 4
- Rao, N.S. (2004) M.V.Sc., thesis submitted to the Acharya N.G. Ranga Agricultural University, Hyderabad.

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Anatomy of the Tongue of Cat (*Felis Catus*)

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Gross anatomical and biometrical studies have been made on the tongue of Indian civet cat by Sarma *et al.*, (2009), Jagapathi Ramayya *et al.*, (2000) and in ruminants by Gupta *et al.*, (1989). However, the information on the tongue of cat is found to be meager. Hence, the present study was undertaken to elucidate the number, distribution of papillae and morphometry of the tongue of cat.

Materials and Methods

Gross anatomical studies were conducted on the tongue of six adult Indian cats, which were brought to the Department of Pathology for postmortem examination. Tongues were collected immediately after death. Thereafter different gross anatomical and biometrical observations were recorded.

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Results and Discussion

The tongues were pale pink in color in fresh state and contained 3 parts viz., apex, body and root. The tip or apex of the tongue was round in shape. It was gradually thinned towards anterior end. In contrast, the apex of the tongue was pointed in cattle and spatula shaped in the horse (Sissons and Grossman, 1975). Its ventral surface contained a fusiform cord like structure called "Lyssa". Similar findings were also reported by Besoluk *et al.*, (2006) in cat and dogs, Miller *et al.*, (1964) and Nickel *et al.*, (1986) in dogs. The body of the tongue was wider than the apex. *Fossa linguae* and *torus linguae* were absent.

The *dorsum linguae* was covered by five different types of lingual papillae viz., filiform, fungiform, circumvallate, foliate and lenticular papillae. Filiform papillae of different sizes were distributed mainly on the dorsum of the tongue but these were absent at the lateral edges and for a short distance on the *dorsum linguae* near the apex of the tongue. These papillae were larger and spine like at the anterior part of the body, whereas the size of papillae gradually decreased towards the posterior part of the *dorsum linguae*. All the filiform papillae were inclined caudally. Boshell *et al.* (1982) reported that the base of each papilla exhibited several conical processes at the tip of the tongue in cat. They opined that filiform papillae were used for grooming of fur in cats.

The fungiform papillae were button like and they were distributed more on the lateral edges and posterior 1/3rd between and in front of the circumvallate papillae, few in the middle 1/3rd and very few at the anterior 1/3rd of the *dorsum linguae*.

Number of circumvallate papillae varied from 4 to 6 in number and they were located at

the posterior end of *dorsum linguae* and equally distributed on either side of the caudal part of *dorsum linguae*. These were rounded in shape at its free surface and were surrounded by a trench. Lakhar *et al* (1989) stated that tongue of ruminants in general contained higher number of circumvallate papillae than those in monogastric animals.

There were two foliate papillae, each located at the lateral margin of the tongue just in front of the anterior pillars of soft palate. Lenticular papillae were located at the caudal part of the *dorsum linguae* near the root of the tongue.

The average length of tongue in cat was 5.8 cm and width was 1.2cm, 1.8cm and 1.6cm at apex, body and root of the tongue respectively. In the present study free and fixed portions were almost equal in size. In goat the ratio of free and fixed portions was 1:4 (Jagapathi *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

References

- Besoluk, K., Eken, E and Sur, E. (2006) *Vety. Medicina*. **10**: 485-489.
- Boshell, J.L., Wilborn, W.H. and Singh, B.B. (1982) *Acta. Anat.* **114**(2): 97-105
- Gupta, S.K., Sharma, D.N and Bharadwaj, R.L. (1989) *Indian. J. of Anim. Sci.* **59**: 1085
- Jagapathi Ramayya, P., Iyyangar, M.P., Gopinath, S and Chandrasekhara Rao, T.S. (2000) *Indian. J. of Vety, Anat.* **12**: 32
- Lakhar, K., Chakraborty, A. and Bhattacharya, M. (1989) *Indian. Vety. J.* **66**: 954
- Miller, M.E., Christensen, G.C., and Evans H.E. (1964) *Anatomy of the dog*. W. B Saunders company. Philadelphia. pp. 654
- Nickel, R., Schummer, A and Seiferle, E. *The Viscera of the Domestic mammals*. Verlag paul Parey, Hamburg. 1986. pp: 57
- Sissons and Grossman. (1975) *The Anatomy of the Domestic Animals*. Vol. 1, 5th Edn, W.B. saunders company, Philadelphia. pp.1538